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D.3.3

COLLABORATION METHODOLOGY WITHIN LOGISTICS CLUSTERS

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
EC	European Commission
PO	Project officer
GA	Grant Agreement
WP	Work Package
4PLs	Fourth party logistics provider
LSPs	Logistics service providers
LL	Living Lab
UK	United Kingdom
TEU	Twenty Foot Equivalent Unit
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
LDCT	Lille Dourges Combined Transport
P&G	Procter & Gamble
VSM	Value Stream Mapping
TEN-T	Trans European Transport Networks
FOC	Full Operational Capability
3PL	Third Party Logistics Provider
GB	Great Britain
Mt	Million Ton
LDCT	Lille Dourges Combined Terminal
UTI	“Unité de transport intermodal” (Intermodal Transport Unit)
GER	Germany
T	Ton

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Executive Summary

The current document aims to explain and to particularize how a collaborative methodology within logistics clusters could be built towards the introduction of the innovative concept of the “*massification*” project. The present document is considered as the outcome of Task 3.2 ‘Demand driven roles and local governance for smart specialized logistics clusters’, and it will be a living document that will be updated before starting each one of the three Living Lab interactions.

The scope of Task 3.2 into the Work Package 3 envisions to share, to test and to validate the outcomes throughout the Living Lab 2. The presented experiences related to the collaborative methodology in WP3, have also to be reapplied in and between logistics clusters in the Living Lab 2. Furthermore, it has to be ensured that the activities within Clusters 2.0 are compliant, fair and sustainable.

Task 3.2 targets in developing demand driven roles and local governance models of smart logistics clusters composed of shippers, fourth party logistics (4PLs) and logistics service providers (LSPs). Within a logistics cluster, regional shippers are invited to adopt common rules in order to better synchronise and optimise their logistics flows. The developed methodology will demonstrate the benefit to bundle volumes on the same train to shippers.

The purposes and objectives of Task 3.2 of the WP3, as stipulated above, are presented in detail, so as to realise what are the main opportunities and challenges in attaining a successful collaboration within logistics clusters.

1 Introduction

1.1 Document structure

The scoping document D.3.3 of the task 3.2 into the WP3 is structured as follows:

In Chapter 1, an introduction to Task 3.2 is provided and defines the purpose of the document and the intended audience.

Chapter 2 outlines the description of the “*massification*” project, in which the collaborative methodology within logistics clusters will be built upon. In order to better understand Task 3.2, a definition and a detailed description of the project genesis and its aims, is highlighted throughout its geographical environment.

Chapter 3 details how the organized workshops assisted in experimenting the “*massification*” pilot. Thanks to these workshops, some key issues were addressed and important outcomes were defined.

Finally, the conclusion triggers the next tasks linked to Living Lab 2 and the partners involved.

1.2 Purpose of Document

This document aims to explain the collaborative methodology of the Task 3.2 in the WP3, which has a clear interaction with the Living Lab 2.

It will define this approach throughout the innovative concept of the “*massification*”. Indeed, the “*massification*” of flows does not narrow or constrain logistics flows bundling. It deals with collaboration between groups of stakeholders.

The ambition of the Task 3.2 is to go through each step to reach two final goals: collaboration for sharing train slots and duplication of the massification methodology to other hubs on the TEN-T corridor to implement in the LL2.

Thanks to the description of each workshop, the collaboration methodology will be drafted and issues will appear. Regarding the experience of these workshops, some recommendations for further duplication will be addressed.

Based on the Task 3.2 description in the Clusters 2.0 GA, the following questions should be taken into consideration and tackled:

- ⇒ What is the volume exported or imported by each shipper?
- ⇒ What is the destination of each volume and where does it come from?
- ⇒ According to the volume shipped between hubs, what are the lanes to test in priority?
- ⇒ Which volume can be guaranteed by the shipper?
- ⇒ At what rate should the vehicles be filled to operate a lane efficiently?

- ⇒ What are the transport modes that will be utilized?

Obviously, the following questions should be also tackled:

- ⇒ How pre and post carriage should be handled?
- ⇒ How shippers can purchase bundled volumes together?
- ⇒ Should shippers be supported by a trustee and how?
- ⇒ Which organisation can locally play the trustee role?
- ⇒ What kind of gain sharing model should be applied between shippers?

1.3 Intended audience

The document is addressing to the Clusters 2.0 project partners with a public dissemination level. For confidentiality reason, some information will not be disclosed in the core of the document but it will be placed in the annex.

2 The Massification Project: genesis and aim

2.1 Definition

The massification is about bundling the flows of several companies (industrial shippers or retailers) for shipment to the same destination in order to increase the utilisation of transport capacities. The “*massification*” concept, implemented into the Clusters 2.0 project, is based on using the modal shift in order to encourage companies towards a new way of shipping and a new way of perceiving its logistics organization (figure 1).

Figure 1: General massification concept

The massification concept, as stipulated in figure 1 above, is widely based on the Physical Internet Concept which highlights the bundling approach in order to reach an efficient, sustainable, flexible and resilient logistics system (figure 2).

Professor Benoit Montreuil developed the new concept of The Physical Internet on 2012 that lays today the target of ALICE, the European technology platform dedicated to logistics.

Figure 2: Physical Internet Initiative based on the Introduction of the Physical Internet, 2012

The massification pilot aims to develop a new collaborative methodology and supports a group of shippers to bundle their goods on a same train towards one destination (figure 3).

Figure 3: Goods massification experienced in the Task 3.2

Nowadays, the “*massification*” is generally used in the transport plan to gather goods at one location. The massification concept implemented in the Clusters 2.0 project is more complex. Indeed, the “*massification*” into a logistics organisation aims to bundle goods on the same transport mode with a capacity. It is relevant to trial the concept on the railway as the “*massified* transport mode”.

However, the logistics community seems to be reluctant to adopt the massification approach in its logistics organisation due to several reasons:

- ⇒ Overall lack of multimodal transport knowledge in Small and Medium Enterprises and sometimes in Key Accounts.
- ⇒ High cost of break loading.
- ⇒ Rail freight is not sufficiently flexible (organisation, delivery, controls). Rail freight suffers steadily from a lack of reliability and its long and complicated administrative procedures.
- ⇒ Rail freight demands a new organization in the whole supply-chain

Even if the “*massification*” project yearns for demonstrating the feasibility of a rail shift, nowadays the combined rail and barge remains under-utilized due to a lack of awareness.

Massification advantages and disadvantages

The “*massification*” approach, implemented in Clusters 2.0, comprises a wide range of advantages that constitute a strong argument to support the related mind shift in the logistics market.

Even if the use of another transport mode generates adjustments in the logistics organisation, the ambition of the experiment is to demonstrate and to argue that the “*massification*” could be a strong competitive advantage for the user. Meanwhile, the “*massification*” project aims to confirm a huge potential impact on load-factor and intermodality:

Table 1: List of massification advantages

ADVANTAGES	IMPACT TARGET
COST	<p>Reductions of the transport cost => costs are divided per unit.</p> <p>Increase of the filling rate with a TEU => it is costly to use 3 trucks half-empty than shipping goods in only one unit on the train.</p>
ENVIRONMENT	<p>Reduction of energy consumption and pollutant emission per ton-km for door-to-door connections with the use of the intermodal freight.</p> <p>Bundling of volumes improves the load factor and enables the shifting of freight from road to rail => fewer trucks on the road.</p> <p>Less noise since the road freight is reduced</p> <p>Improvement of the CSR.</p>
ORGANISATION	<p>Optimisation of logistics schemes that enable more flexibility with the use of different freight mode => higher reliability.</p> <p>Bundling volumes aim to improve business and logistics models through the sharing approach: vehicles, resources, one single</p>

	point of contact.
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Like most of innovative practices, the massification approach comprises also some disadvantages:

Table 2: List of main massification disadvantages

Need to fight a resilience to change: a mind shift is inevitable since transport plans are broadly shaken up with railway mode.
Without commitment between shippers, the massification cannot work.
Complexity of using the railway mode because of a multiplicity of stakeholders: rail operators, rail companies, terminal operators, leasing, typology of boxes, container renters, path booking in France (SNCF). This is more complex when the connection is not created like Dourges and Barking.
Without sufficient volumes, the massification brings no sense.
Costly transportation mode compared to truck. Arguments for shifting transportation mode have to be solid.
Not all goods on a train are compliant for the Channel Tunnel for the case Dourges – Barking (chemical products...)
To determine a good business model, shippers have to provide data which remain sensitive and often confidential. It brings more complexity to the massification approach

2.2 Context and environment

The “*massification*” project has been under experimentation since 2015 in the Hauts-de-France region with the support of Euralogistic. Euralogistic is the regional logistics cluster, which aims to promote logistics and supply-chain companies and to disseminate logistics good practices.

The “Pôle d'excellence regional Euralogistic” disseminates and promotes its expertise through the whole Hauts-de-France region towards:

- Companies (logistics operators, freight, industries, distribution, e-business...)
- Harbors and logistics platforms
- Training and research centers
- Local communities, prescribers
- Professional centers and employment stakeholders

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The Euralogistic staff proposes fully integrated offers to stakeholders and provides networking between companies, training, and research for structural and innovative projects.

Euralogistic was created in 2003 by the Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Artois network. Since the beginning, Europe, state, regional council, territory and companies have supported Euralogistic.

Its headquarters is located on the Campus regional Euralogistic, center of excellence near the European multimodal platform DELTA 3 in Dourges. It is located at the crossroads of the second French logistics area, in the core of a 100 million-inhabitant pool around 300kms (between Paris, London and Brussels).

Euralogistic owns several awards and is involved in different organizations:

- National award winners of logistics innovation in Paris in 2013,
- DATAR (inter-ministerial delegation dedicated to the territorial planning and to the regional attractiveness) label of remarkable cluster companies,
- Co-founder of French logistics inter-clusters,
- Elected as the European logistics clusters representative inside ALICE (Alliance for Logistics Innovation through Collaboration in Europe) consortium.

Euralogistic places itself as a leader to promote human skills and Hauts-de-France supply-chain and logistics image through a regional and international frame.

The region Hauts-de-France benefits from competitive logistics advantages (figure 4). At the heart of Northern Europe, the Hauts-de-France is the second-largest logistics region in France with strong road, waterway and rail networks linked with neighbouring countries: Belgium and the UK.

The Hauts-de-France region with the sole inland tri-modal platform in France is an excellent place to experiment the “*massification*” approach.

Figure 4: The logistics map of the Hauts-de-France region

The inland multimodal platform is located in Douges in Delta 3 area. Delta 3 owns the logistics area with several warehouses of well-known shippers and is a public organisation. The multimodal terminal is operated by a private company, LDCT (Lille Douges Combined Terminal), which is based 20 km to the south of Lille near the main motorway, A1 (figure 5). It comprises two railway lines and 14 tracks with its shunting yard. The storage area has a capacity of about 2500 TEU. There are also two docks with a direct connection with a large gauge canal linked with main northern ports.

The terminal railway network enables the connection with several hubs in the south of Europe. Other lanes have to be developed in further months like “the *massification* line”.

Figure 5: LDCT railway network

2.3 Genesis of the pilot project

Since its creation, Euralogistic has been aiming to provide good practices and to inspire and motivate logistics stakeholders in innovative projects in order to increase their competitiveness, their cost efficiency and their sustainability. However, this mission remains a challenge because logistics companies do not have the same level of expectation and awareness regarding new issues that have to be tackled: carbon foot print reduction, CSR increment, sharing the cost of optimising their whole organisation.

With this in mind, Euralogistic has succeeded in gathering a group of shippers around a table in order to present the innovative approach: the “*massification*” project. The freight modal shift represents one of the main issues that Euralogistic strives to tackle: the multimodal transportation as one solution to reduce some logistics constraints.

The “*massification*” project started in 2015 as response to a demand of a shipper: Procter&Gamble expected a regional logistics cluster support to identify other shippers with a similar need. Indeed, P&G aimed to increase rail freight flows from 20% to 50% shipped from its Amiens’ plant (the second main city in the region). Nonetheless, achieving such an

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increment could be feasible only if other shippers would commit to load goods on the same train.

As a result, Euralogistic launched this groundbreaking concept of massification starting from the multimodal platform of Dourges with the strong Procter & Gamble collaboration and commitment.

3 Collaboration within clusters and shippers: steps and methodology

The development of a collaboration methodology within a cluster has to be deployed throughout the experiment of the “*massification*” project. Bundling goods flows on a same train relies strongly on the group of the shippers’ willingness to collaborate. If no collaboration is achieved, the “*massification*” approach will not be feasible, since the essence of the project relies on commitment and collaboration.

This chapter aims to describe gradually the path to achieve collaboration and the launch of the “*massified*” train, based on several workshop meetings.

Afterwards each meeting description, three main outcomes will be highlighted in order to have a better overview on progress or blocking points.

3.1 Methodology and approach

The methodology of the massification project is defined regarding an experimentation process. In order to set up the massification project, Euralogistic had to gather a sufficient number of relevant stakeholders.

The identification of relevant stakeholders was defined according several criteria:

- Size of shippers (volumes)
- Geographic area: regional level for the using of Dourges terminal
- Range of shippers
- Level of rail freight awareness

This assessment of the relevant target allowed establishing a large list of shippers to be invited by phone. Lastly, 20 shippers came to an awareness meeting about the massification project. Through this meeting, Euralogistic succeeded in identifying willing contributors to be involved in the massification project. Step by step, the organization of round tables, workshops allowed to refine the experiment and to have a progressive approach. Each meeting aimed to assess improvement point or blocking point in order to define a methodology to steer a “*massification*” group.

3.2 Stakeholders involved into the project

At the beginning of the project, Euralogistic managed to invite a group of 15 shippers. The methodology used to gather some shippers will be detailed in the following sub-chapter 3.2.

Nowadays, we experiment the pilot with a group of 7 shippers still involved since 2015.

These shippers are mainly located in the Hauts-de-France region. All of them are important stakeholders in the region with several warehouses and a sufficient volume to consider the adoption of and participation in the massification project. Different business sectors are represented:

Table 3; List of shippers' typologies

GLASS MAKING
AGRICULTURE / VEGETABLES
TYRES
WATER
SPORTSWEAR
HARDWARE AND DECORATION RETAILER
CONSUMER GOODS RETAILER

For confidential reasons, shippers will not be named in the document, except for Procter & Gamble, which is a full partner of the Clusters 2.0 project as well as a member of this group of shippers. However, the thorough list of these shippers is available in the Annex 1.

3.3 The massification experiment step by step

The massification experiment followed a collaborative round table meeting methodological approach, towards the organisation of consecutive face-to-face meetings. This part of the document aims to describe thoroughly the outcomes of each meeting with the shippers mentioned above in order to address different issues and outcomes that will be stated in the following sub-part.

3.3.1 2015 meetings

- 01/13/2015: First awareness meeting

The first meeting was organised at the beginning of 2015 at Euralogistic premises. It dealt with presenting the massification project to a group of regional shippers (see annex 2) in order to raise their awareness.

A VSM of the massification project was presented to the group, to highlight the collaboration issue in gathering goods (figure 6):

Figure 6: VSM of the massification

Ten shippers composed the first massification group.

Procter & Gamble moderated the meeting since the project started following its own demand.

The main purpose of the workshop was to acquire a more comprehensive understanding of shippers' expectations and to investigate whether a collaborative way of working could accommodate their needs.

The meeting was divided into three topics:

- ⇒ Which is the point of view on intermodal transport?
- ⇒ Which are the main issues to tackle?
- ⇒ Which destination could be relevant for the group?

The discussion highlighted some blocking points:

- ⇒ Shippers do not have enough volume to fill a train
- ⇒ Corridor frequency is not sufficient enough
- ⇒ Corridor schedule is not synchronised with shippers' needs (impact on

- delivery)
- ⇒ A lack of knowledge about freight operator services
 - ⇒ Reliability, information and tracking are the key point for shippers
 - ⇒ The high cost of rail

During the meeting, shippers were also asked to provide some data (volume/ departure/ destination) in order to assess the destination most relevant for the project. A confidential agreement was signed between the parties-even if Euralogistic is a public organization-, as it allowed the strengthening of an already strong confidence relationship with the group.

Finally, a list of intermodal hubs was addressed inside the TEN-T corridors:

- ⇒ Milano
- ⇒ Bologna
- ⇒ Zaragoza
- ⇒ Duisburg
- ⇒ Zeebrugge
- ⇒ Barking

At the end of the meeting and following the discussions made, a projected timetable was defined:

ACTIONS	DUE DATE
Decision to attend the massification project or not	01/23/2015
Definition of data excel sheet to be sent	01/23/2015
Preparation of a confidential agreement for sharing data with Euralogistic	02/14/2015
Filling out the excel sheet	02/28/2015
Analyze of complete data and identification of the most relevant connection	03/31/2015
Debriefing meeting and visit of the Dourges container terminal	15/04/2015

Nonetheless, this timetable was not fully followed. Indeed, the massification project relies on the capacity of shippers to be proactive and involved. The availability of each shipper is the *condition sine qua non* to succeed in the project. **Shippers are the key.**

- 05/29/2015: Second awareness meeting

For this meeting, initially scheduled on April, an official invitation letter was sent to gather a wider group of shippers. However, this invitation letter in French (see annex 3) was sent to a list of identified shippers. Fifty shippers were called in order to present the aim of the meeting and to encourage them to attend.

Thanks to this addressed invitation, Euralogistic succeeded to gather a group of 15 shippers

and the massification project was officially presented.

Main outcomes following those both meetings:

- ⇒ Understanding shippers expectation
- ⇒ Identification of rail freight constraints
- ⇒ Confidential agreement to provide data

- **10/06/2015: Data analysis**

This meeting aimed to provide a synthesis of data analysis from shippers who accept to deliver some.

Since the main identified destination remained the UK, some shippers were not interested to pursue the massification pilot. Indeed, some shippers had more flows towards other destinations.

Figure 7: Map of main relevant destination for shippers

The figure seven indicates through red arrows the 6 most relevant destinations for shippers regarding the data provided. It occurred that the UK was the first destination followed by Germany, Italy, Spain, Poland and Greece.

The repartition of destination is represented below (figure 8):

Figure 8: Destination and volumes' repartition of goods shipment

The presentation of this data analysis depicts that UK has to be the destination to choose. The pilot has been also experimented between the Dourges and the Barking terminal.

In parallel with the restitution workshop, Euralogistic proposed to present an IT tool that could have a benefit for the massification approach. This tool aimed to demonstrate advantages of collaboration on a “data sharing platform”.

Additionally, Nallian was introduced to the group of shipper. Nallian is one of the Clusters 2.0 partners and contributes by optimizing its Cargostream platform. Nallian is an IT provider which supports companies by providing a Data Sharing Platform.

The meeting concluded with the decision that 9 months were required to define the best connection for the experimentation of the first pilot of a massified train in Europe.

Main outcome regarding the meeting:

- ⇒ Identification of the UK destination for the pilot
- ⇒ Main destinations on the TEN-T corridors
- ⇒ Introduction of IT platform too early

3.3.2 2016 meetings

There were two meetings in 2016, as detailed described below:

- **04/27/2016: 4PL introduction**

The UK has been identified as the best opportunity to succeed in the massification project. However, shippers questioned the organization model to launch a massified train:

- ⇒ Who may organize flows with shippers?
- ⇒ How to deploy a gain sharing model?
- ⇒ What is about backhaul?

During this meeting, Euralogistic proposed to introduce three 4PL to shippers in order to choose the best stakeholder to support this innovative project.

As a public organization and a neutral body, Euralogistic is subjected by law to introduce 3 stakeholders to the group. However, Euralogistic did not encourage any choice.

The list of the proposed three 4PL is presenting below:

- ⇒ A French company
- ⇒ An American company
- ⇒ An English company

At the end of each individual presentation, a round table was organized to assess shippers' feedback. The French company was the most relevant to support the project for several reasons:

- ⇒ Flows orchestration expertise
- ⇒ Multimodal expertise
- ⇒ A collaborative manner of working and significant references
- ⇒ Trustee role

However, the French 4PL suffered from a lack of the UK market awareness.

Consequently, no decision was made during the meeting, as a new question was risen: Does the group of shippers really want to work with a 4PL?

Euralogistic decided to keep in touch with the French 4PL in order to have a first draft of their methodology to support the pilot between Dourges and Barking.

Main outcome regarding the meeting:

- ⇒ Need to define the business model
 - ⇒ Shippers' interest confirmed
 - ⇒ Introduction of 4PL too early
- **10/06/2016: Brainstorming**

At this step of the experimentation to implement a massification methodology with the group of shippers, Euralogistic realized that the project was facing blocking points. In fact, Euralogistic did not know what the following step could be. Since the beginning of the project, as an orchestrator, Euralogistic has always been a force for bringing forward proposals. Several tracks were explored without concrete results. The shippers and we felt a

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kind of frustration. In addition, the agenda of this meeting aimed to let shippers expressing themselves. This meeting marked the beginning of concrete results thanks to the listening.

Regarding the previous meeting, the support of the French 4PL did not comply with the massification project.

Hence, this workshop was dedicated to assess real shippers' expectation regarding the pilot.

The following three topics were addressed to shippers:

- ⇒ The massification and your company
- ⇒ Delta 3 platform
- ⇒ From theory to practice

The aim of this workshop was to ask the right targeted questions to shippers. Euralogistic felt that the interest of shippers was fading away. In order to understand their willingness, this workshop was the opportunity to let shippers expressing themselves, by providing their views on the aforementioned three topics.

- The massification and your company: shippers' answers
 - ✓ Deep willing to pursue the massification approach for its CSR advantage
 - ✓ The multi-modality a strategic issue
 - ✓ Need to accelerate the project
 - ✓ To assess and to measure gains, the cost between Dourges and Barking has to be clarified in order to identify threshold effect
- The Delta 3 terminal
 - ✓ Delta 3 as a strategic location, in the core of main corridors
 - ✓ Ideal infrastructure based on 3 modes
 - ✓ A strong development capacity
 - ✓ A non-transparent Delta 3 service offer: need a better awareness of connection availability
- From theory to practice
 - ✓ Conduct a business case to determine a raw price and the break-even point regarding a potential filling rate
 - ✓ Define if Dourges could be operational in case of sufficient volume
 - ✓ Shape the massification model: safety, quality of service, frequencies, turnaround, lead-time, pre and post-carriage, freight-forwarder, 4PL, gain sharing...
 - ✓ Grow and widen the shippers group
 - ✓ Take into account backhauling
 - ✓ Write a volume engagement letter for each shipper

This workshop enabled the project to strengthen, thanks to a strong willingness expressed

by shippers.

As a result, the draft agenda has been defined as following:

ACTIONS	WHO?	DEADLINE
Conduct an economics and technical feasibility study	Euralogistic and consultant	February 2017
Confirm the feasibility of the rail network between Dourges and Barking	Euralogistic and LDCT (Dourges terminal)	November 2016
Check the anti-trust issue	Shippers	November 2016
Fill a sheet with each shipper's goods constraint	Euralogistic and shippers	December 2016
Find other shippers to broaden the group	Euralogistic	December 2016
Work on a letter of intent	Euralogistic and shippers	December 2016

Main outcome following the meeting:

- ⇒ Listening shippers is the first requirement
- ⇒ Understanding shippers expectation
- ⇒ Definition of clear steps forward

3.3.3 2017 meetings

The 2017 year was an efficient and fruitful year for the massification project, as a number of constructive meetings took place

- ⇒ 2 meetings with French shippers
- ⇒ 2 consulting assignment through public tender
- ⇒ 1 visit of 2 terminals in the UK
- ⇒ 1 meeting with English shippers in the UK
- ⇒ 1 dissemination of the project during the International Physical Internet Conference in Graz (Austria)

- **03/17/2017: Technical and economic feasibility study**

Following the discussions during the previous meeting with the group of shippers, Euralogistic launched a public assignment for a technical and economic feasibility study regarding the lane Dourges – Barking. As public organization, Euralogistic was committed to conduct a public tender. Three consultants expressed their interest to support the group.

Among the three available propositions, Euralogistic chose a French consultant with a strong expertise in intermodal transportation and particularly in the railway sector. Mn'L Consulting expressed a strong interest to be involved in such an innovative and disruptive project and to share its experience to support the shippers.

The first workshop of the 2017 year was the opportunity to present consultancy conclusion.

The aim of the study was:

- To seize the technical issues for the lane: terminals, material, traction, wagons, length, gauge, tunnel
- To define the best frequencies
- To define the break-even point
- To provide recommendation for management solution

The selected consultant introduced the study to shippers with a focus on terminal, railway, wagon technical data, time schedule, costs and questions. Results of the study to assess the technical and economic feasibility of the train are detailed below:

Barking is 310 km far away from Dourges (figure 9).

Figure 9: Map of distance between Dourges and Barking

Crossing the channel tunnel is the best way to reach Barking terminal. Nonetheless, the channel tunnel is constraining in terms of material (figure 10). Thus, the train has to be composed by 18 wagons, with a wagon train length of 650 meters and a weight of 1400t.

Figure 10: Train gauge for the Channel Tunnel

As a result, there is no technical barrier to cross the tunnel except an agreement from Europorte/ Eurotunnel.

Regarding each shipper's constraints, a fact sheet was sent to shippers in order to ensure technical recommendation and to schedule the best turn around and best frequencies. All assumptions were also based on 3 and 5 trains per week with 80% and 100% filling rate.

⇒ **Turn around and schedule:**

- 45 operation weeks per year
- Use of the fast railway during the night
- Schedule: departure from Dourges at around 9:00 PM and return to Dourges at 8:00 AM => AB time schedule

Since 2015, the time schedule has been improved with an AB travel, which will allow best frequencies and freight optimization.

In order to reduce the overall cost, the "classical" railway could be used with an obvious impact on the travel model: from AB to AC

⇒ **Costs**

Table 4: Cost per UTI based on a 100% filling rate

SYNTHESE 1 : remplissage à 100%				
Exploitation				
		45		
Nombre de train		135		225
Nombre UTI par train		36		
TRACTION				
	3 x sem	12600	5 x sem	11890
Chantier				
	DGS	177		177
Manut	BK	25		25
Manut	DGS	39,4		39,4
WAGONS				
	33€xwxj	216810	38€xwxj	249660
Coût d'approche		8000		8000
Prix traction par UTI				
		350		330,3
Chantier par UTI				
		4,9		14,4
Manut 1+2				
		64,4		64,4
Wagons				
		46,26		53,0
TOTAL PAR UTI				
		465,57		462,09

The overhead table sheet (table 4) outlines a cost per container with a 100% filling rate assumption. The cost comprises operation, traction, handling and wagons still based on 3 or 5 turn around per week.

The following sheet (table 5) outlines a cost on 80% filling rate basis.

Table 5: Cost per UTI based on a 80% filling rate

SYNTHESE 2 : remplissage à 80%			
Exploitation			
		45	
Nombre de train		135	225
Nombre UTI par train		29	
TRACTION			
	3 x sem	12600	5 x sem 11890
Chantier			
	DGS	177	177
Manut	BK	25	25
Manut	DGS	39,4	39,4
WAGONS			
	33€xwxj	216810	38€xwxj 249660
Cout d'approche		8000	8000
Prix traction par UTI			
		434,48	410,0
Chantier par UTI		6,1	14,4
Manut 1+2		64,4	64,4
Wagons		57,42	65,8
TOTAL PAR UTI		562,41	554,61

The general overview of the cost linked with the massification project responded to shipper's expectation. The presentation of the study enabled to reassure shippers and to reinforce their commitment into the project.

***Nota bene:** Euralogistic paid the economic study and technical review for the freight lane from Dourges to Barking assigned to MN'L consulting since it was launched before the official start of the Clusters 2.0 project. However, in a technical point of view, Euralogistic and the Chamber of Commerce own the whole report. Nonetheless, for the benefit of the massification approach and the stake of the multimodality opportunity, Euralogistic delivers the report only if all partners of the Clusters 2.0 project respect the confidential issue.*

Nonetheless, the consultant and shippers raised some questions:

- ⇒ Volume engagement?
- ⇒ Which gain sharing model?
- ⇒ Which 4 PL?
- ⇒ What about the Brexit issue (customs, business impacts)?
- ⇒ What about the backhauling?

The next meeting was also scheduled at the end of June in order to present what kind of support Euralogistic would be able to provide regarding the main issue to tackle: the backhauling.

Main outcomes following the meeting:

- ⇒ Demonstration of the connection feasibility
- ⇒ Below 80% filling rate, no economic sustainability
- ⇒ Backhauling has to be taken into consideration

- 06/27/2017: Backhauling from the UK, consulting support

The English market is known for its weak exportation's rate. Main trucks coming from the UK are empty because of the flows imbalance.

The sustainability of the project relies ineluctably on the backhauling issue.

On June, Euralogistic lead a study on the area catchment of Barking terminal. This survey highlighted the weakness of Barking terminal activities and its lack of attractiveness. Thus, the issue to identify potential backhauling from Barking could be tougher than perhaps compromised.

After some research, another terminal was identified and seemed to be more relevant to attract English shippers on the massification project. The terminal is located 150 km away from Barking in the North West of London, in Daventry known as DIRFT (figures 11-12). The terminal was built 5 years ago and owns modern infrastructures.

Daventry benefits from its strategic location in “the core” of the UK. Indeed, Daventry is located inside the “Logistics Golden Triangle”. Logistics activities are growing fast inside the triangle and the opportunity to identify other shippers remains more relevant.

Figure 11: Location of Barking and Daventry

Figure 12: Malcolm Logistics rail network (Malcolm is operating one of Dirft Terminal)

“The UK coverage offered by rail services handled through DIRFT allows users to hub core flows, for example connecting Northern Italy to Scotland with minimal delay and removing the need to serve each destination with separate services when volume may not make it viable.”¹

The following figure 13 emphasizes all logistics stakeholders located in DIRFT and confirms the strong potential to find relevant shippers who could have an interest in the *massification* project.

¹ Reference : Prologis and Malcolm Group

³ Reference : Prologis

Table 6: Cost synthesis based on 100% filling rate to Daventry

SYNTHESE 1 : remplissage à 100%						
Exploitation		45				650m
Nombre de train par an		135		225		1400 tbr
Nombre UTI par train		36				
TRACTION par sens	3 x sem	12135	5 x sem	11400		-4% vs Barking
Chantier	DGS	177		177		
Manut	DAVENTRY	30		30		25 à 30€
Manut	DGS	39,4		39,4		3 free days
						puis 10€ per unit per day
WAGONS	36€xwxj	216810	38€xwxj	249660		
	95 Kkm		140 Kkm			420km par trajet
Cout d'approche		9000		9000		IT + GE
Prix traction par UTI		337,08		316,7		
Chantier par UTI		4,9		4,9		
Manut 1+2		69,4		69,4		
Wagons		46,46		53,2		
TOTAL PAR UTI		457,86		444,21		

Table 7: Cost synthesis based on 80% filling rate for Daventry

SYNTHESE 2 : remplissage à 80%						
Exploitation		45				
Nombre de train par an		135		225		
Nombre UTI par train		29				
TRACTION par sens	3 x sem	12135	5 x sem	11400		-4% vs Barking
Chantier	DGS	177		177		
Manut	DAVENTRY	30		30		25 à 30€
Manut	DGS	39,4		39,4		3 free days
						puis 10€ per unit per day
WAGONS	36€xwxj	216810	38€xwxj	249660		
	95 Kkm		140 Kkm			420km par trajet
Cout d'approche		9000		9000		IT + GE
Prix traction par UTI		418,45		393,1		
Chantier par UTI		6,1		6,1		
Manut 1+2		69,4		69,4		
Wagons		57,68		66,1		
TOTAL PAR UTI		551,63		534,68		

Since Daventry is located in the core of the UK railway network, several connections with the northern of England are possible, like the ones presented in the figure 14 below:

Figure 14: DIRFT terminal schedule

Direction	Routes	Services	Transit	Normal Cut-Off	Collect From
WEEKDAYS					
NORTH	DIRFT to Grangemouth	7 Days	Overnight	20:30	07:00
NORTH	DIRFT to Mossend	5 Days	Overnight	17:00	02:30
SOUTH	Grangemouth to DIRFT	7 Days	Overnight	17:30	05:00
SOUTH	Mossend to DIRFT	5 Days	Day	04:30	17:00
WEEKENDS - Grangemouth Service					
NORTH	DIRFT to Grangemouth	7 Days	Day	09:30	23:00
SOUTH	Grangemouth to DIRFT	7 Days	Day	08:00	23:00
SUNDAY					
NORTH	DIRFT to Grangemouth	7 Days	Overnight	20:00	07:00
SOUTH	Grangemouth to DIRFT	7 Days	Overnight	13:00	08:30

Thanks to these several studies, shippers could seize all opportunities to reach the whole UK market with a price focus.

In the meantime, Europorte was introduced to the group of shippers in order to get feedback regarding safety and security of the Chanel tunnel. Indeed, during 2014, the tunnel was assaulted by migrants because of a lack of barriers and control area.

Today, Fréthun (the last location before the tunnel access) is secured thanks to the improvement of infrastructures. Thanks to the testimony of Europorte, shippers were reassured for the feasibility of the train.

In conclusion, Euralogistic presented two potential consultants who could support the massification project through the identification of English shippers in order to balance flows. One consultant was a French expert (Overlog.eu) of the UK market and the other one was English (Railfreight Consulting) with an obvious UK market acknowledge.

English consultants had a strongest expertise since they were involved into the previous connection between Dourges and Barking. As it was explained before, the line was interrupted because of safety issue. Therefore, Railfreight Consulting proposed to support the project through the following approach as depicted also in figure 15:

Figure 15: English consultant approach

This meeting aimed to answer shipper's questions which have been raised since a lot of months:

- ⇒ Train cost on a round-trip basis with 2 filling rates hypothesis
- ⇒ Gain more opportunity to attract back hauling if Daventry terminal is considered
- ⇒ Safety and security are now guaranteed
- ⇒ Back hauling will be assessed and identified thanks to the English consultant's support

A huge step was taken throughout this meeting since it enabled the strengthening and confirmed that the massification project could be realistic. Shippers gained confidence and more enthusiasm (pictures of the meeting can be found in annex 4).

Main outcomes following the meeting:

- ⇒ A terminal has to be attractive with a dynamic catchment area to increase chance to identify backhauling
 - ⇒ Identification of Daventry platform
 - ⇒ Need to identify English shippers with a consulting support
- **12/20/2017: Awareness meeting in the UK**

Euralogistic launched a public tender to finally determine the consulting company. As a public organization, it was subjected to public purchasing law.

The UK consulting company was ranked first among candidates with higher allocation criteria: methodology relevance, the project team credentials and skills, total amount of the proposal.

The consultant has to bring its multimodal expertise and its UK market knowledge regarding

following items:

- ⇒ Key data of main UK sectors and location with exportation (spirits, tobacco, agro-food, retail)
- ⇒ Identification of companies with contact details of the appropriate person of logistics decision-making (supply-chain manager, European transport manager)
- ⇒ Identification off all logistics stakeholders who could support the project in the UK (association, prescribers...)
- ⇒ Increment companies' awareness on the massification approach by phone and inviting them to a meeting with Euralogistic.

Three high points were scheduled:

- ⇒ A kick-off meeting for framing the consulting assignment
- ⇒ A mid-term meeting
- ⇒ A final feedback meeting

The kick-off meeting held in London in October in order to enjoy visits of Barking and Daventry terminals. The aim was to assess the relevance and the attractiveness of both terminals. The visit of Barking terminal confirmed also the outcomes of the research and survey done: a terminal with empty spaces and ageing infrastructures. Some pictures are available in the Annex 5.

Afterwards, a visit in Daventry was made, in order to have a better overview of the activities occurred. It appeared that the terminal is growing fast with modern infrastructure, huge warehouses and big logistics companies. Those both visits reaffirmed the great opportunity to continue the connection from Dourges to Daventry via Barking.

The mid-term meeting was organized in London in December in order to sensitize some English shippers to the massification approach. The meeting was led by Euralogistic with the support of consultant.

Nonetheless, even if consultants succeeded to identify 80 relevant stakeholders, only 4 shippers attended the meeting because of the Christmas period. At the same time, consultants were allowed to speak on behalf of the other identified shippers. The full list of named shippers is available in the Annex 6.

During this meeting, Euralogistic introduced the massification project and its purpose. The meeting aimed to seize the potential interest of the selected stakeholders to shift their flows from road to train with a bundling methodology.

All attendees and Railfreight Consulting on behalf of other shippers, expressed broadly a strong interest to better synchronize their flows in using the railway. Dourges platform remained a good opportunity for the UK shippers to reach Southern Europe. The environmental aspect represented an important issue that the railway could improve.

However, if advantages were **easily** demonstrated, shippers asked several questions:

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- ⇒ Which business model?
- ⇒ Which business offer?
- ⇒ Who is in the lead?

At this step of the massification project, Euralogistic was not able to clarify or to answer these questions that are the key element for the success of the project.

Euralogistic proposed to organise a bilateral meeting with French shippers in few months when the offer will be defined.

Finally, this meeting remained positive since all logistics stakeholders were enthusiastic and hurried to go further (pictures of the meeting are provided in annex 7).

Main outcome following the meeting:

- ⇒ Strong interest from the UK side regarding the massification project
- ⇒ Need a clarification of the business model (technical and operational)
- ⇒ Organize a bilateral meeting (English and French)

3.3.4 2018 meetings

Three workshops were organized with shippers and were marked by a sharp acceleration in the massification progress.

- **03/28/2018: Backhauling identification feedback and introduction of Dourges freight operator**

This workshop aimed at highlighting the actions lead by Euralogistic in the frame of the massification project between Dourges – Barking and Daventry. Then, Railfreight Consulting restituted the study dedicated to the identification and awareness of companies with sufficient export flows from the UK to the North of France. Lastly, Euralogistic fostered the discussion between shippers, regional facilitators and stakeholders regarding the implementation process of the connection between Dourges and the UK (pictures of the meeting and the list of attendees are provided in annexes 8 and 9 respectively).

Feedback on Euralogistic's action:

On 2017, Euralogistic hired Mn'L Consulting to assess economic and technical feasibility of the project. It occurred that the connection could be feasible. However, even though the line can be economic sustainable and efficient, the question of the backhauling remains the key issue to definitely reach balanced flows.

In order to increase the chance of success, Euralogistic identified other possibilities to find backhauling. After having assessed the catchment area of Barking, Euralogistic had a look on other terminals. A deeper study demonstrated the strong opportunity of Daventry platform.

In order to go further, Euralogistic hired English consultants to support the group of shippers to reach balanced flows.

All these missions and studies allowed to:

- ⇒ Confirm the technical feasibility of the lane
- ⇒ Determine the break-even point of the massified train
- ⇒ Define solution of organization and recommendation
- ⇒ Identify data of strategic sectors
- ⇒ Identify prospective backhauling and decision-making contact
- ⇒ Organize a meeting in the UK with English shippers to present the massification approach

Restitution of the study assigned to Railfreight Consulting:

- ⇒ A strong potential of export flows identified in the Mid-West (Daventry area)
- ⇒ Shippers, 3PL, 4PL, carriers and terminal operators were surveyed. Numerous stakeholders express their interest in the massification project (figures 16 & 17)

Figure 16: Chart of distribution's identified stakeholders

Figure 17: Scheme of potential English users

Clusters 2.0

As explained previously, the different actions held by the consulting company, confirmed a real stake from English stakeholders to be involved in a project such as the massification pilot since it is an innovative, collaborative and sustainable manner to ship.

However, the consultants addressed several recommendations based on their own experience.

⇒ They would suggest that the key considerations are:

- ✓ Define and confirm preferred train formations, service & destinations
- ✓ Define base train price BY TENDER & Agree commercialisations
- ✓ Approach the identified opportunity in UK & Implement in stages

⇒ They would suggest this to be procured via a Managing Agent to:

- ✓ Offer independence & Consolidate volume from several different sources
- ✓ Competitively procure both the haulage and wagon provision
- ✓ Avoid over-reliance on a FOC or terminal manager

Discussion with regional logistics stakeholders

Novatrans, LDCT and Europorte were invited for this meeting since progress allowed beginning discussions with other stakeholders who will be obviously involved in the train launching.

Novatrans explained to the group shippers the reason why the first attempt to connect Dourges to Barking failed in 2014.

As noticed previously, Novatrans and Europorte confirmed the sudden stop of the train because of migrants. However, it was underlined that the train was almost competitive even after only 6 months: delivery, costs, filling, and H1 highway speed.

According to Novatrans and Europorte, the massified train could be reliable if volumes are sufficient. Novatrans expressed a strong interest to operate the train from Dourges and to provide its price to the group of shippers.

Nonetheless, some questions should be taken into account:

- ⇒ Which 4PL? An expert provider or a regional?
- ⇒ Do shippers want to work with their own carriers or carriers with a multimodal expertise?

After this discussion, shippers agreed to work with a 4PL and carriers recommended by Novatrans.

Lastly, Europorte and Novatrans will provide during the next meeting a cost based on a door-to-door solution and pre and post-carriage with their margin.

All shippers appreciated this meeting and the progress achieved. The feasibility of the train

seems to be more realistic and feasible.

The next meeting was scheduled for the 15th of May 2018.

Main outcomes following the meeting:

- ⇒ A strong potential of export flows identified
- ⇒ Interest from regional stakeholders to support the project towards a success
- ⇒ Need to identify a 4PL and carrier companies with an intermodal expertise

• **05/15/2018: The missing meeting**

As scheduled during the previous meeting, the workshop for the cost offer was held on May. However, one day before the meeting, Eulogistic was informed that Novatrans and LDCT would not attend, due to the national railway agency (SNCF) strike that caused many hassle in the all rail freight organization. Moreover, during the meeting, Europorte announced that no cost would be provided.

This missed meeting generated a real frustration for all shippers who were all expecting an offer. It could have been critical for the project progress but finally shippers were ensured about its success.

After several discussions with Europorte, all agreed to schedule the next meeting for the 20th of June either physically or by phone (pictures of the meeting and the list of attendees are provided in annexes 10 and 11 respectively)

Main outcomes following the meeting:

- ⇒ To be more watchful on the group leading
- ⇒ Keeping shippers motivated is inevitable
- ⇒ Communication between stakeholders has to be managed

• **06/20/2018: Presentation of the Railfreight operator's service offer**

Even if the previous meeting failed because of a lack of feedback from the operator, almost all shippers were gathered either in our premises or by phone (see Annexes 12-13: list of attendees and pictures of the meeting)

The whole meeting was led by Novatrans since it dealt with the presentation of the offer.

The service offer

NB: Due to the business confidentiality, the cost provided by Novatrans will not be revealed. No agreement has been given.

The offer is based on a connection between Dourges and Barking. Two offers were presented:

- ⇒ A 1100 ton train composed by 15 wagons with 30 containers with a higher cost
- ⇒ A 1500 ton train composed by 20 wagons with 40 containers certified for the channel tunnel

The offer is based on 100% filling rate. However, the provided cost is indicative and there is a need to be adjusted with each shipper.

The price does not comprise the container renting, the pre and post-carriage.

Novatrans suggested a transport schedule based on 5 rotations which could fit with the national transport plan linked with southern France (see figure 5 further above). The more there are rotations, the more the cost will be reduced.

This proposition represents a strong advantage for some shippers.

Shippers have to engage themselves for a 3 years' period towards Europorte and GB Railfreight. This engagement is contractual and not commercial.

Novatrans emphasized on the commitment aspect. To have a concrete offer, shippers will have to provide a commercial engagement.

Regarding the connection between Barking and Daventry, Novatrans and Europorte came to an English shipper that has a daily train between both terminals. Five slots could be available on a round trip. A cost offer is still expected from this shipper. If the offer is too costly, Novatrans would strive to find another solution.

Locks to be raised and backhauling issues

Regarding the carrier's choice, Novatrans recommended to write a call for interest. However, shippers were actually launching their tender to carriers that could be inhibiting. Shippers assign carriers a certain volume and duration in a tender process. The launch of the train could be postponed because of these contractual reasons towards carriers.

Novatrans asked shippers if they would agree to commit in partnership business model in order to be independent. Novatrans offered to support the group with its dedicated law service.

To go further, Novatrans offered as well to be a full partner in the project. Indeed, Novatrans proposed to own a part of the train in order to minimize the risk for shippers. Novatrans will be in charge to sell some slots independently the shippers group if the business model is a partnership-based approach.

For two shippers, the question of the backhauling cost must be taken into consideration. Indeed, the cost of the carriage in the UK is extremely low. So, in order to attract English shippers, the price for the train should be "competitive". In addition, it means that the cost in both trips would not be equal: from Dourges, the price will be higher than the price from Barking to Dourges. A clever business model will have to be built.

Finally, yet important, the BREXIT could also be seen as a great opportunity for the rail

freight since eastern truckers will not be allowed any more to join the UK territory.

At the end of the meeting, a draft was addressed as following:

ACTION	DEADLINE	WHO
Identification of shippers, carriers, 3PL who used the first connection from Dourges to Barking	July 2018	NOVATRANS
Barking and Daventry terminals visit	4 th of July 2018	NOVATRANS/EUROPORTE/LDCT
Individual interviews with shippers	Mid-July	NOVATRANS/SHIPPERS
Business offer	September 2018	NOVATRANS
Expected engagement of shippers	September 2018	SHIPPERS
LAUNCH OF THE TRAIN BEGINNING OF 2019		

All shippers were fully satisfied by the massification progress. Now it is up to shippers, Novatrans and Europorte.

Main outcomes following the meeting:

- ⇒ Shippers expectation respected
- ⇒ Service offer provided
- ⇒ Volume ad partnerships engagement strongly required at this step

3.4 Outcome and solution

Throughout all those workshops organized during the last 4 years, Euralogistic experienced the massification process and enabled the provision of outcomes.

The current sub-section 3.4 will be divided in three points, based on the different stakeholders' involvement in the project:

- ⇒ Shippers
- ⇒ Neutral body
- ⇒ Third party

Shippers

Euralogistic managed to maintain a sufficient group of shippers in spite of the four years' duration of the project. It is risky to lead a project on such a long period. During the two meetings, in October 2016 and in May 2018, the project failed to be interrupted because of two main reasons:

- ⇒ A lack of concrete actions
- ⇒ A lack of communication

The involvement of shippers and stakeholders remains a key point to succeed in such a collaborative project. In order to strengthen the group cohesion, meetings have to be **concrete, efficient and active**. Otherwise, the next steps would be vague without a clear purpose.

In the Dourges-Barking pilot, Euralogistic faced twice these situations and time was wasted. It created frustration and a loss of confidence in the project.

However, it must be reminded that the massification project relies only on the shippers' decision: go or no go. The project progress is punctuated by shippers 'schedule: time to get answer, definition of an appropriate date of meeting. All these hazards have to be taken into account.

In order to progress, shippers have to be motivated to become proactive stakeholders rather than being followers. In the massification pilot, some shippers are deeply involved and others are silent. Without a strong willingness of shippers, it remains tough to engage a collaborative project. **Willingness, motivation and proactivity are inevitable** to reach the common goal: shipping bundling volumes in order to reduce cost, to increase CSR and to improve logistics organisation.

Moreover, in the group of shippers, the level of interest to succeed in the massification project is patchy. Some shippers own more volumes than others and it represents an added motivation to bundle volumes since the issue is huge.

At the beginning of the project, Euralogistic sent the invitation directly to decision-making contacts or the person with a decision power. When the confidential agreement was signed for sharing data, time was gaining since all shippers owned the same level of "decision" and signed during the meeting.

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In order to go further in the commitment process, Euralogistic recommends the encouragement of shippers to support the project economically. This would strengthen their engagement and their confidence in the project. During the massification experiment, this kind of engagement has never been clearly asked. Shippers are still waiting for a proof of real stake. This is a sensitive aspect of the project: asking for budget or not will depend on each project. Since the Dourges-Barking remains a pilot project, this financial issue was not a blocking point.

Neutral body

Euralogistic has played a role of a neutral body since 2015. As a public organisation, Euralogistic subjects to a duty of confidentiality and cannot sway the opinions or the willingness of the group of shippers.

In the case of the massification project, the neutral body is considered as a facilitator. Regarding the GA, a neutral body could be one or several entities that have a dense network of shippers to gather around the project: logistics clusters, a Chamber of Commerce, a public entity and so on.

In the massification approach, being a neutral body requires active listening to shippers in order to respond to their needs. The neutral body has to remain a leader in order to create a dynamic for stimulating interest and further opportunities. Indeed, the success of such groundbreaking project relies firstly on shippers. That is why a good cohesion is inevitable.

Third party

As third part, we mean other stakeholders who could be involved in the project.

Regarding the several meetings organized, Euralogistic could regret having introduced a third part in a non-relevant period. For this specific case, the need of shippers was not taken into account. It dealt with the presentation of an IT provider, Nallian (Clusters 2.0 partner) and 4 PL.

Nallian was introduced to the group of shippers in the third meeting in order to present its platform, CargoStream. This platform aims to map more relevant massified corridor regarding the gathering of shippers 'data.

However, to three main issues were faced:

- ⇒ Firstly, the group of shippers was not enough mature at this step of the project. The interest of this IT tool was not clearly understood and it created confusion. So, it is necessary to progress step by step according to shippers 'expectations. However, in the next meetings, Euralogistic would invite shippers to connect to CargoStream to receive real-time bundled transportation proposals. This proposition would be addressed when the progress is sufficient to understand the potential interest. Nevertheless, at this step of the Clusters 2.0 project, the CargoStream platform does not seem to be sufficiently mature to be introduced in the massification group. Some proof of work needs to be demonstrated before inviting shippers to connect on the platform.

Clusters 2.0

- ⇒ Secondly, the neutral body has to remain neutral and cannot sway on shippers 'decisions to provide data on the CargoStream platform. As a public organization, Euralogistic subjects to public procurement and has to present a minimum of three potential partners. If this regulation is not applied, Euralogistic could be exposed to the risk of prosecution. In the case of the introduction of a consultant for the UK support, only two companies were introducing following a last moment cancellation. So CargoStream could be introduced regarding the GA, but Euralogistic has to respect its legal framework
- ⇒ Finally, the highest issue remains is the availability and disclosure of 'data'. For each shipper, data are serious. Disclosing data represent a high risk for each company. So, the CargoStream platform has to be thoroughly secured and safety to ensure shippers to provide data on a cloud tool. This topic represents an acute point for shippers.

However, Euralogistic succeeded in gathering shippers 'data in order to map the most relevant destination to experiment the massified train. Data were gathered on an excel sheet, after the signature of a confidential agreement. Probably shippers were ensured by the public body role or by the neutral body role.

In June 2016, Euralogistic introduced three 4 PL to the group of shippers in order to identify a support for the organisation of the massified train. Once again, the period remained no relevant for shippers. First, shippers expected the cost for the train in order to decide to be involved in the massification project. Even if the massification approach represents a great opportunity for shippers' logistics organisation and sustainability, the price is the legitimate argument. Throughout this experience, Euralogistic understood at this step that the progress of the project has to rely on shippers' expectations and must be listened. That is the key of the success.

Figure 18: Synthesis of the massification milestone from 2015 to 2018 and main outcomes per workshop

MAIN OUTCOMES PER WORKSHOP

01/13/2015 05/29/2015	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding shippers expectation • Identification of rail freight constraints • Confidential agreement to provide data
10/06/2015	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of the UK destination • Main destinations on the TEN-T corridors • Introduction of IT platform too early
04/27/2016	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need to define the business model • Shippers' interest confirmed • Introduction of 4PL too early
01/06/2016	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Listening shippers, first requirement • Understanding shippers expectation • Definition of clear steps forward
03/17/2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstration of the connection feasibility • Below 80% filling rate, no economic sustainability • Backhauling has to be taken into consideration
06/27/2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Terminal has to be attractive to increase chance to identify backhauling • Identification of Daventry platform • Need to identify English shippers with a consulting support
12/20/2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong interest from the UK side regarding the massification project • Need a clarification of the business model (technical and operational) • Organize a bilateral meeting (English and French)
03/28/2018	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A strong potential of export flows identified • Interest from regional stakeholders to support the project towards a success • Need to identify a 4PL and carrier companies with an intermodal expertise
05/15/2018	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To be more watchful on the group leading • Keeping shippers motivated is inevitable • Communication between stakeholders has to be managed
06/20/2018	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shippers expectation respected • Service offer provided • Volume and partnerships engagement strongly required at this step

3.5 Next steps

At this step, no further meeting is scheduled for the Dourges – Barking project. In few weeks, Euralogistic will have more information from Novatrans which is finalizing actually the offer per shipper regarding other stakeholders: 4PL, carrier companies, GB Railfreight and Tesco. The last call confirms the strong willingness of Novatrans to succeed in the pilot project.

Regarding the Clusters 2.0 project, the methodology developed throughout the massification project has to be duplicated to other hubs in the frame of Living Live 2:

- Duisport
- Zaragoza
- Bologna
- Trieste
- Trelleborg
- Piraeus

In result, Euralogistic presented at the end of July the purpose of the massification project and its methodology to Duisport, the hugest inland multimodal platform in Europe. This meeting enabled the testing of the methodology for the first duplication. Duisburg represented a great interest for French shippers and a line could be created between Dourges and Duisburg. The meeting remained fruitful and a draft agenda was defined (see annex 14).

For other hubs, a schedule will be soon defined during the next LL meeting lead by Procter and Gamble.

4 Conclusions

The present study is a living document, which aims to provide a methodological framework on of how volumes will be bundled on regional TEN-T hubs and between them.

Nowadays, logistics clusters are seen as value creators for regions and for territorial development, well established in the core of good intermodal connections, logistics platforms with large freight volumes like Zaragoza, Duisburg, Bologna, Dourges like other mature clusters represent a great opportunity for growth, employment and competitiveness, strengthening economic and social development.

However, those well-placed logistics clusters still do not leverage enough their full potentials in terms of business and sustainability in a European scale. Logistics clusters have to play an important role in minimizing negative impacts such as congestion, noise, land use and local pollution.

So, Clusters 2.0 aims to create and to strengthen a network of logistics clusters in a hyper-connected multimodal logistics network in order to improve transport efficiency, load factors and modal shift, providing reliable and sustainable intermodal services in European supply chains. Also, the massification project which trials a bundling methodology represents a strong opportunity to foster connections between logistics clusters in Europe. Through the utilization of intermodal transport which responds to sustainability, reliability and resiliency issue, massification has to be deemed as a great tool to create a better interconnected clusters network. Moreover, the massification is also about strengthening collaboration between stakeholders and logistics clusters. Collaboration and intermodal transport represent a strategic key and a great opportunity to create a better synchronized connection network between logistics clusters.

Through the massification project, which was developed with the support of Euralogistic thanks to P&G demand, a new way of collaboration, is being experimented to reach a common goal: Optimisation of transportation plan, reduction of carbon foot print, and improvement of the freight cost in a collaborative approach.

The lead of the massification project remains a huge challenge since it deals with a pilot project without any previous experience. The guarantee of a success is not assured even if great opportunities are created.

The massification project cannot be narrowed to a bundling volumes methodology. The massification embeds broadly a collaborative methodology. To enhance shipper's collaboration with each other represents a great challenge as well as a great opportunity. However, massification advantages are solid arguments to commit each other. Since the beginning of the project, all shippers have endorsed to collaborate with each other for the stake of the project.

The bundling project remains also bold, breakthrough and disruptive. Indeed, the massification project started from shippers' needs that are not common in the logistics schemes. In the massification project, shippers speak directly with the rail freight operator and the terminal manager. Usually, shippers are only in touch with their logistics providers who handle directly all rail freight stakeholders. This new scheme upsets tradition which represents a new disruptive model. Moreover, gathering only shippers in the massification

Clusters 2.0

project fosters a collaborative approach. Euralogistic could have decided to gather different stakeholders such as carriers, 3PL, 4PL, but it remains risky since the approach would be commercial and the lead of the project would be compromised.

Now, the pilot is evolving in a good dynamic and concrete results are expected on September 2018 with the support of the regional rail freight operator. One issue, which needs to be tackled during the next meeting, is gain sharing.

The gain-sharing model guarantees shippers a fair sharing regarding engaged volume. It represents a strategic key in the massification approach since it brings benefit to the collaborative methodology.

Lastly, organizing different meetings with a variety of shippers enables to build a kind of a broader methodology, able to be duplicated in other TEN-T hubs.

The massification approach brings a great opportunity to other hubs and clusters since it allows sensitizing shippers to the multimodality transportation as an answer to social, economic and environmental issues. It enhances shippers to assume an active role in their logistics organization rather than delegating to logistics providers. The massification project creates a solution to rationalize flows between hubs, to ship smoothly and to improve connection relying on shipper's demand. Moreover, massification can bring new business opportunities throughout the creation of line, for instance between Barking and Dourges and by extension a connection between Barking and the rest of the continent.

The European policy context might indicate that the usage of the railway mode could be a great opportunity. Indeed, it seems that a regulation can endorse the eastern truckers who would be narrowed in some territory or limited in terms of number in a company. For instance, the Brexit represents a huge opportunity for the pilot between Dourges and Barking. Lastly, the road hauler sector suffers from a truckers' scarcity and the haulage companies will have to face with this new phenomenon.

The methodology linked with the massification project in Dourges has to be adapted regarding the business, environmental and geographical context.

Lastly, the Dourges-Barking massification project remains a pilot with its own specificity regarding:

- Terminal infrastructures
- Rail connection
- Location
- Range of companies
- Geography
- Regional stakeholders willingness
- Chanel tunnel
- Customs issue
- Creation of the line

In result, it means that it doesn't exist only one massification but several *massifications*.

A massification project relies on different specific criteria and is unique. Moreover, a massified connection could be an opportunity to create a line which could not be feasible without bundling flows. So, goods massification could be seen as an economic leverage for

different region since it could enable new connection and new business.

ANNEXES

Annex 1: List of shippers, location and typology of goods

SHIPPER	LOCATION	TYOLOGY
ARC INTERNATIONAL	ARQUES (PAS DE CALAIS)	GLASS MAKING AND TABLEWARE
BONDUELLE	VILLENEUVE D'ASCQ (NORD)	VEGETABLES
BRIDGESTONE	BETHUNE (PAS DE CALAIS)	TYRES
DANONE WATERS	EVIAN (HAUTE-SAVOIE)/ DOURGES	WATER
DECATHLON	DOURGES	SPORTSWEAR
LEROY MERLIN	DOURGES	HARDWARE AND DECORATION RETAILER
PROCTER & GAMBLE	AMIENS	CONSUMER GOODS RETAILER

Annex 2: List of attendees on the first meeting in January 2015

ARC INTERNATIONAL
BONDUELLE EUROPE LONG LIFE
BRIDGESTONE
CARGILL CTL
DANONE WATERS
DECATHLON
JOKEY
PROCTER & GAMBLE
PPG INDUSTRIE
SAINT GOBAIN GLASS LOGISTICS
GROUPE SOUFFLET
TOYATA
VALLOUREC
TEREOS

Annex 3: Invitation letter to the first official massification meeting

Euralogistic, Delta 3, LDCT et Procter & Gamble lancent en équipe :

UNE OPERATION DE MASSIFICATION DE FLUX MULTIMODAUX

VENDREDI 29 MAI 2015 de 10H30 à 12h30 – Campus Euralogistic

Lieu : CAMPUS EURALOGISTIC - Pôle d'Excellence Euralogistic - Etage 1 - Plate-forme DELTA 3 de Dourges

INVITATION PERSONNELLE A CET ATELIER DE COLLABORATION - NON REDIFFUSABLE

La multinationale **PROCTER & GAMBLE** a demandé au **POLE D'EXCELLENCE EURALOGISTIC** de rechercher plusieurs industriels et distributeurs du Nord de la France pour collaborer à ce projet très opérationnel. En lien avec DELTA 3, nous vous invitons donc à participer à un atelier de travail préalable à la **construction d'une opération de massification de flux logistiques**.

L'objectif est d'explorer les possibilités de **combinaisons et de compatibilités de flux de transport multimodaux de marchandises**. Partant d'hypothèses concrètes, des envois massifiés **inter-usines** ou **via des plates-formes** seront planifiés sur **certaines destinations** (aller/retour) en particulier vers :

- Le sud de la France,
- L'Italie, l'Espagne, l'Allemagne, l'Angleterre et le Benelux

Au sein d'un groupe de chargeurs industriels et de la distribution, venez partager, **de manière confidentielle**, vos réflexions sur ce sujet en vue d'envisager une collaboration potentielle.

- **10h30** – Tour de table des industriels et PME présents
- **10h45** – Introduction par Procter de la séance de travail
- **11h15** – Temps d'échange avec les participants
- **12h30** – Prochaines étapes, timing et clôture

Réunion organisée par :

En collaboration avec :

COUPON-RÉPONSE ENTREPRISE

MASSIFICATION DES FLUX LOGISTIQUES : Le 29 mai 2015, à 10h30 à Dourges

Annex 4: Pictures of the meeting held on June 2017

Annex 5: Pictures of Barking and Daventry platforms

BARKING TERMINAL

DAVENTRY TERMINAL

Annex 6: List of attendees and sensitized shippers in the UK during the meeting held in December 2017

Attendees:

- ✓ DB Schenker
- ✓ Tate&Lyle
- ✓ Solstor
- ✓ Danone in order to represent French shippers

Railfreight Consulting represented:

- ✓ Russel Group
- ✓ Nestlé Group
- ✓ British Steel
- ✓ DFDS
- ✓ Unilver
- ✓ Tarmac
- ✓ Bywaters
- ✓ CEMAT

Annex 7: Pictures of the massification meeting in the UK, 20/12/2017

Annex 8: Pictures of the meeting on the 28th of March 2018

Annex 9: List of attendees on the 28th of March 2018

SHIPPERS	REGIONAL FACILITATORS	OTHERS
BONDUELLE	NOVATRANS (Dourges rail operator)	Railfreight Consulting
AJINOMOTO (new)	LDCT (Dourges terminal operator)	Regional Chamber of Commerce
DANONE	DELTA 3 (real estate)	Mn'L Consulting by phone
PROCTER&GAMBLE	EUROPORTE (tunnel operator)	Euralogistic

Bridgestone, Decathlon and Arc International were not unfortunately available.

Annex 10: List of attendees on the 15th of May 2018

BRIDGESTONE
BONDUELLE
DANONE WATERS (4 attendees)
IDEO (Danone's 3PL)
MN'L CONSULTING
PROCTER AND GAMBLE
DECATHLON
DELTA 3

Annex 11: Pictures of the meeting, 05/15/2018

Annex 12: List of attendees on the 20th of June 2018

IN EURALOGISTIC'S PREMISES	BY PHONE
NOVATRANS	DANONE WATERS
EUROPORTE	IDEO
LDCT	MN'L CONSULTING
BONDUELLE	PROCTER&GAMBLE
DECATHLON	BRIDGESTONE

Annex 13: Picture of the meeting on June 2018

AGENDA FOR THE FIRST MASSIFICATION MEETING IN DUISPORT**1. Analyze and map shippers in Duisburg**

- a. Information from the sales department
- b. Independent research following several criteria:
 - ⇒ Size
 - ⇒ Branch
 - ⇒ Volume (estimated)
 - ⇒ Flows (estimated)

Due time: mid-August

2. Selection/ Evaluation

- a. Who should be invited?
- b. Open the selection to the catchment area

Due time: beginning of September

3. Prepare invitation based on the Dourges invitation

- a. Definition of a date linked with the availability of shippers
- b. Attendance of P&G (testimony) and Euralogistic
- c. First contact with main customers of Duisport to seize their potential interest (e.g Evonik)

Due time: mid-September

4. Hold a meeting in Duisport

- a. Gather shippers
- b. Get data and volumes to assess flows towards Dourges

Due time: end of September / beginning of October

5. Evaluation meeting (afterwards the first meeting) in Dourges which could be combined with WP3 meeting

- a. Questions, interest, feedback
- b. Exchange with Dourges

Due time: to define, ideally end of October, beginning of November

